

STATUS OF OUTREACH SPORTS PROGRAM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS FOR OUT-OF -SCHOOL YOUTH AMIDST PANDEMIC: PERSPECTIVE TO COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

DARWIN D. OFRIN

darwin.ofrin@lspu.edu.ph

Laguna State Polytechnic University San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study enquired to ascertain the status of outreach sports program in Higher Education Institutions for out-of-school youth amidst pandemic: perspective to community development. The researcher used the descriptive correlational design to describe the data, characteristics used and the population in the study. It was conducted at the SUCs in Region 4A purposively selecting 120 PE teachers. The findings are as follows: The person-related factors do not affect the OYS program and Youth Development. The correlation of Perceived implementation of outreached sports program for out-of-school youth (OSY) is interpreted as “Implemented.” The correlation of Level of Compliance with Minimum Health and Safety Standards is interpreted as “To a Great Extent.” The correlation of Level of Effectiveness of the Outreached Sports Program to Out-Of-School Youth Development is interpreted as “Highly Achieved.” The relationship between the compliance with the minimum health and safety standards of the Outreach Sports Program for Out-of-School Youth and its effectiveness for OSY development are found “Significant.” The relationship between the compliance with the minimum health and safety standards of the Outreach Sports Program for Out-of-School Youth and its effectiveness for OSY development are found “Significant.” The results of the regression analyses on the Implementation of Outreach Sports Program Affecting the Overall Effectiveness of OSY development are also found “Significant.”

Keywords: OSY Program; Life Skills; Youth Development; Health Standard; Sports